

PRESS RELEASE

22.09.2025

Citizens' Assembly in Ljubljana

On **12 June 2025**, migrants, refugees, asylum seekers, and representatives of organizations working on participation, inclusion, and integration – alongside public officials and international actors – gathered in **Ljubljana** for a **Citizens' Assembly on the political participation of migrants**.

The Assembly provided a platform to discuss the challenges of participation, inclusion, and representation in Slovenia, while fostering collaboration to develop practical solutions. Participants engaged in constructive dialogue, sharing experiences and perspectives on how to strengthen democratic involvement and ensure equal opportunities for all.

In the second part of the event, attendees divided into **four thematic working groups** focusing on:

- housing
- language
- racism and discrimination
- working conditions and labour rights

Each group examined the barriers faced by migrants and proposed ideas to improve policies and practices in these areas.

The Citizens' Assembly in Ljubljana highlighted the importance of inclusive dialogue and collective problem-solving, underscoring the need to ensure that migrants' voices are heard in shaping democratic processes.

Citizens' Assembly in Vienna

On **15 June 2025**, more than 150 participants from 29 countries gathered in Vienna for the People's Assembly **"Solidarity is Our Common Ground."** The Assembly provided a powerful space for democratic deliberation and collective imagination across borders.

Migrant and mobile workers joined young climate justice activists, artists, and organisers to strategise around shared challenges, roles, and hopes. Together, participants reflected on the political and social consequences of the 2024 European elections, while resisting divisive narratives that attempt to pit migrant, labour, and climate justice against one another.

Discussions centred on **key questions** such as:

- What alliances and capabilities are missing in our contexts?
- How can each organisation play to its strengths in the wider ecosystem of social change?

Insights that emerged included the need for stronger narrative power and alternative media, expanded political education and training, structures of care and conflict mediation, and long-term coalition-building through cross-sector collaboration.

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Citizens' Assembly in Thessaloniki

On **27 June** and **12 July 2025**, the CITIDEM Project successfully hosted Citizens' Assemblies in **Thessaloniki, Greece**, under the theme **"Democracy vs. Disinformation in the Digital Era: Addressing Disinformation and Enhancing Citizen Participation Online."** The events brought together citizens and experts to reflect on the growing challenges posed by digital disinformation and to explore solutions for strengthening democratic participation.

The Assemblies fostered dialogue and collaboration, encouraging participants to share perspectives and co-create ideas for a more informed and participatory society. In the second part of the event, attendees divided into **four thematic working groups**:

Understanding & Mapping Disinformation

This group focused on identifying the nature and sources of disinformation. Participants explored the types of false information most commonly encountered, the platforms and actors responsible for its dissemination, and the broader societal and democratic consequences of its spread.

Combating Disinformation - Policies, Tools & Education

This group examined existing efforts to counter disinformation, including legal frameworks, technological tools, and educational initiatives. Participants assessed the effectiveness of current measures, identified gaps or shortcomings, and proposed innovative solutions to strengthen the fight against disinformation.

Strengthening Citizen Participation & Public Trust

This group addressed the erosion of public trust in democratic institutions and the decline in civic engagement. Participants discussed the barriers that prevent citizens from participating in democratic life and brainstormed strategies to foster inclusion, rebuild trust, and empower citizens to act as watchdogs against disinformation.

Media Literacy & Critical Thinking in the Digital Age

This group explored the role of education and public awareness in building resilience to disinformation. Participants discussed the institutional support needed to integrate media literacy into formal and non-formal education, the importance of equitable access to resources, and the role of community spaces such as libraries and youth centers.

By the end of the session, the assemblies had produced a set of policy recommendations. These proposals reflected not only the knowledge gained but also the collaborative spirit of the assembly. They demonstrated how informed and engaged citizens can contribute meaningfully to public debate and policymaking.

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Online Civic Education Program

On **5 September 2025**, the CCR team hosted another online civic education program for citizens. Together with **Christos Levaditis**, Project Manager and Coordinator at United Societies of Balkans, the session explored tools and mechanisms for participatory democracy.

Christos shared inspiring approaches to fostering active engagement at the local level and **highlighted the meaningful role that volunteers play in shaping communities**. The conversation examined how citizens can participate more effectively in democratic processes and reviewed their impact across several member states.

An interactive session allowed participants to share their views on key questions, enriching the discussion and offering diverse perspectives. The program underscored the **importance of civic education in strengthening democratic participation and building more inclusive societies**.

On Friday, **23 June 2025**, a thoughtful discussion was held with two experienced youth workers on **the vital role of NGOs in fostering participatory democracy**. The exchange provided valuable insights into the challenges and opportunities youth workers face when reaching out to young people and offered reflections on the true meaning of active citizenship.

The conversation underscored the **importance of youth engagement in shaping a more inclusive and democratic society**. Participants shared experiences and ideas that highlighted how NGOs can serve as bridges between young citizens and democratic processes, ensuring that their voices are heard and their contributions valued.

This inspiring dialogue reaffirmed the crucial role of youth participation in building resilient communities and strengthening democratic practices. By sharing experiences and perspectives, the discussion highlighted how young people, supported by NGOs, can act as catalysts for social change

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